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*Tetyana Valyukevych***LINGVO-STYLISTIC ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH SLANG
IN GENERATION Z COMMUNICATION**

The article examines the linguo-stylistic features of English slang used by Generation Z in modern digital communication. Particular attention is paid to the influence of social networks, internet culture, and global cultural processes on the formation and development of slang expressions. The study analyzes the communicative functions of slang, identifies main factors contributing to the emergence of new slang units, such as popular culture, globalization, and digital communication technologies. The research highlights the role of slang as a tool of self-expression and social identification among young people. The results demonstrate that slang represents a dynamic component of modern language and reflects linguistic transformations happening under the influence of digital communication.

Key words: generation Z, slang, youth language, English slang, linguo-stylistic features, digital communication, social media language, internet slang.

***Валюкевич Тетяна Вікторівна. Лінгвостилістичні особливості
англійського сленгу серед покоління Z.***

Стаття присвячена лінгвостилістичним особливостям англійського сленгу серед представників покоління Z, що формується поза межами традиційних мовних норм і виконує роль засобу неформальної комунікації. Мета статті – проаналізувати лінгвостилістичні особливості англійського сленгу, що використовується поколінням Z, з урахуванням його функціонального навантаження, комунікативних стратегій та впливу цифрових технологій на його формування та еволюцію. В процесі наукового дослідження використовувалися загальнонаукові методи пізнання, зокрема аналіз, синтез, узагальнення та класифікація. Результати дослідження показують, що сленг є особливим пластом лексики, що постійно змінюється під впливом суспільних і технологічних факторів. Він виконує функцію засобу самовираження та соціальної ідентифікації, особливо серед представників покоління Z, які активно використовують його в цифровому просторі. Встановлено, що основними джерелами формування сленгової лексики є масова культура, соціальні мережі, відеоігри та процеси глобалізації, які

сприяють активному запозиченню іншомовних слів. Досліджено, що молодь цінує сленг за його гнучкість і здатність швидко адаптуватися до змінних умов комунікації. Проаналізовано різні види сленгової лексики, що використовуються поколінням Z. Виокремлено такі основні категорії: скорочення, що спрощують спілкування (наприклад, BRB – be right back); лексичні новотвори, які виникають під впливом цифрових технологій; сленг для емоційного вираження, що передає почуття та настрої; сленг як засіб соціальної ідентифікації, що допомагає розмежовувати групи за інтересами; імітаційний сленг, який модифікує стандартні мовні одиниці; жартівливий сленг, що ґрунтується на іронії та гуморі. Зроблено висновок, що англійський сленг покоління Z є динамічним і багатограним явищем, яке активно розвивається під впливом сучасних комунікаційних технологій і змін у суспільному мовленні. Практичне значення дослідження полягає у можливості застосування його результатів у вивченні сучасних тенденцій розвитку англійської мови та особливостей молодіжного мовлення.

Ключові слова: англійський сленг, покоління Z, лексика, комунікація, соціальна ідентифікація.

Generation Z, which grew up in the era of digital technologies and the Internet, demonstrates a unique communicative experience that significantly differs from that of previous generations. Social networks, online platforms, and digital communication environments have become the primary spaces where new linguistic practices are formed. One of the most distinctive features of Generation Z communication is the extensive use of slang, which functions as a marker of social identity and a means of adapting to changing digital communication contexts.

Youth language is characterized by permanent transformation. However, the excessive use of slang often leads to communication difficulties between different generations. Linguistic innovations emerge and disappear rapidly, and many expressions may be incomprehensible to individuals who are not actively engaged in digital communication environments. This can create barriers in contexts where clarity is required, such as academic or professional discourse.

Therefore, the study of slang as an element of modern linguistic culture is essential for improving communication between different social groups and generations. Understanding linguistic innovations contributes to more

effective communication and promotes mutual understanding in both professional and interpersonal interactions.

The linguo-stylistic features of English slang used by Generation Z have been widely examined in both Ukrainian and international linguistic studies. Researchers focus on the nature of slang, its communicative functions, cultural implications, and the challenges associated with its interpretation and translation.

A significant contribution to the study of slang has been made by T. Viedernikova, who analyzes the linguistic and stylistic characteristics of modern slang and the functioning of American and British slang expressions [9;10]. N. Hlushchuk investigate linguo-pragmatic aspects of modern English slang, including its origins, classification, and semantic features [11]. I. Kozubai examines lexical and structural characteristics of slang used in social networks, which is particularly relevant for Generation Z due to their intensive participation in digital communication [12]. O. Lesinska and I. Holiuk analyze the structural features and evolution of American youth slang [13].

The topic has also been explored by International researchers. U. Ainura, B. Mutanova, and L. Alieva analyze general characteristics and functions of English slang and its influence on contemporary communication [1]. Y. Yusuf and I. Fata investigate the use of slang by Generation Z in social media and emphasize its rapidly evolving nature [7].

Important contributions to the study of slang were made by lexicographers such as Tony Thorne, the author of Dictionary of Contemporary Slang, and Jonathon Green, whose Green's Dictionary of Slang is considered one of the most comprehensive sources on the history and development of slang in the English-speaking world [3; 6].

Modern scholars, including Chloe Combi, Christopher Moore, and Gretchen McCulloch, analyze linguistic behavior and communication patterns of Generation Z, paying particular attention to the influence of digital communication and internet culture on language development [2; 4; 5]. Despite the large number of studies devoted to slang, there is still a lack of systematic research that combines linguistic and socio-cultural aspects of Generation Z slang.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the linguo-stylistic features of

English slang used by Generation Z, taking into account its communicative functions, usage strategies, and the influence of digital technologies on its formation and evolution.

Slang represents a special layer of vocabulary that develops outside traditional linguistic norms and reflects the dynamic character of social communication. It functions as a means of expressing emotions, attitudes, and group identity. According to N. Hlushchuk, slang is used not only by young people but also by representatives of various social groups and frequently appears in mass media and advertising [11].

The formation of new slang expressions is influenced by several factors and the most significant one is popular culture, particularly music and cinema. Musical genres such as rap, pop, and electronic music often introduce new lexical expressions that are quickly adopted by young audiences. Similarly, films and television series contribute to the emergence of slang by introducing expressions associated with fictional characters, cultural references, or narrative contexts [1].

Other important factors are globalization, intercultural communication and video games which play a crucial role in slang formation. The desire of young people to develop their own linguistic codes also contributes to the formation of slang. The use of unconventional vocabulary allows individuals to express their identity, distinguish themselves from older generations, and strengthen social bonds within peer groups [1].

American slang performs several communicative and stylistic functions [13]. It often introduces creativity and humor into communication. For example, the expression *yeet* is used to convey excitement or to describe the act of throwing something energetically [8]. Many slang expressions function as alternatives to standard lexical items. For example, *glow-up* refers to a significant improvement in appearance or personal development, while *tea* denotes gossip or interesting information [8].

Certain slang expressions may express criticism, sarcasm, or negative evaluation. For instance, the word *simp* may carry a negative connotation when describing a person who excessively seeks another individual's approval. Some slang expressions help convey emotions or soften strong language. For example, *heck* may be used instead of the stronger word *hell*, while *fr* ("for real") emphasizes sincerity [8]. According to research

findings, slang may constitute approximately 20% of the vocabulary of an average American speaker [11].

Rapid development of Generation Z slang is largely influenced by digital technologies and social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and Twitter, which enable rapid dissemination of new expressions. Slang terms often become popular overnight and may disappear just as rapidly. For example, the word *lit* (meaning “exciting” or “excellent”) has gradually been replaced by newer expressions such as *rizz* (charisma) or *gyat* (an exclamation expressing surprise) [10].

Despite its widespread use in informal communication, slang remains outside the norms of standard literary English. In academic and professional discourse, the use of slang may reduce clarity and may be perceived as inappropriate due to its informal nature [9; 10].

Generation Z slang can also be classified according to its communicative purpose. Abbreviations and acronyms simplify communication in digital environments. Examples include LOL, BRB, and OMG [13]. New lexical units emerge under the influence of digital communication and internet culture. Emotional expressions help convey emotional states in online communication where non-verbal cues are absent. Identity markers describe social roles or behavioral characteristics within online communities [12]. Imitative slang modifies existing lexical units or adapts them to new contexts. Humorous slang is based on irony, wordplay, and creative combinations of words [7].

Conclusions. Slang represents a distinctive lexical layer that develops outside traditional linguistic norms and functions as an important element of informal communication. It reflects the dynamic processes occurring in modern society and serves as a means of self-expression and social identification, particularly among young people.

Generation Z actively contributes to the formation of new slang expressions under the influence of digital technologies, social media platforms, popular culture, and globalization. The main types of slang include abbreviations, newly formed lexical units, emotional expressions, identity markers, imitative slang, and humorous slang. These linguistic forms demonstrate the diversity of Generation Z slang and illustrate its rapid development within contemporary digital communication environments.

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